

Towards an Alternative Low-Cost Perception System for Aerial Vehicles in Confined Spaces

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel alternative approach to perception for aerial vehicles operating in confined spaces such as ballast tanks. It focuses on designing and implementing a system of small Time-of-Flight (ToF) sensors arranged in an array that could replace conventional, expensive, and bulky 2D or 3D LiDAR systems. Confined spaces often feature narrow, dark, and dusty environments. Here, conventional vision-based solutions fail for autonomous navigation and even basic flight tasks such as obstacle avoidance. Furthermore, carrying conventional LiDAR sensors significantly reduces flight time, especially for small drones (< 2.5 kg). Therefore, this paper proposes a system using VL53L8CX sensors as an optimal alternative, which significantly reduces the weight and computational power. A novel approach is developed to combine 12 of these ToF sensors across two SPI buses. This setup provides a 360° radial field of view within a 4m radius around the aerial vehicle, which is strategically designed to accommodate these sensors. The proposed design is validated and compared against a 2D lidar system for collision prevention in a PX4 SITL simulation of a ballast tank environment. Additionally, the sparsity and accuracy of the generated point cloud are compared with those of 3D LiDAR while flying within a mock ballast tank. This design and study aim to establish a baseline for lightweight, compact, and safe navigation for small drones in confined and featureless environments.

Index Terms—Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Time of Flight Sensors, Confined Spaces, Collision Prevention.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENT advancements in perception technology and miniaturized systems have created a growing demand in aerial robotics that focuses on cost-efficient sensor payloads to maximize flight duration. While it is vital for a vehicle to continuously know its state and surroundings, incorporating a multitude of sensor types is neither practical nor efficient. Typically, decisions regarding sensor selection involve balancing efficiency, weight, and cost. This balance becomes particularly

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Fig. 1: Actual model of the designed quadcopter with attached sensors flying inside mock ballast tank.

crucial for aerial vehicles operating in confined spaces, which are narrow, dark, dusty, and most importantly, GNSS denied [1]–[4]. Hence, the selection of an appropriate perception system must emphasize robustness, reliability, and resilience. Specifically, for vehicles designed to operate within ballast tanks, they should have a small platform area so they are able to navigate through narrow manholes, while ensuring longer flight time for extended inspection tasks [5]–[7]. This leads to an adoption of small to mid-sized aerial platforms, although they are generally not suitable to carry bulky and costly cameras or LiDAR systems [8]–[10]. Hence, there arises a critical need for lightweight, power-efficient sensors capable of delivering effective and reliable perception capabilities within these constraints.

Fast and resilient onboard perception is critical for autonomous robots, as emphasized in several studies like [11]–[14]. However, operating in symmetrical structures and varying lighting environments makes it even more challenging, partic-

ularly when relying on visual cameras [15], [16]. Although event [17] and IR [18] cameras can operate in dark environments, they work best with static obstacles and have a limited field of view. Similarly, ultrasonic and infrared range finders [19], [20] or millimeter-wave radars [21] offer lightweight and cost-effective solutions but suffer from reflectivity and noise within environments such as metallic ballast tanks. Single range finders [22], [23] have frequently been used for obstacle detection in aerial vehicles due to their lightweight and cost-effective characteristics. However, they often provide limited sensing capabilities and are not that robust. More advanced studies have explored multi-zone ToF sensors, notably the VL53L5CX sensors [24], [25]. They demonstrated promising results in terms of accuracy, pixel error rates, and range performance under varying light conditions. Nonetheless, the implementation supports a maximum of four sensors using a single custom interface board. Scaling this approach to use a larger array of sensors for bigger drones with extended cables introduces additional challenges. It includes signal interference, noise, signal loss, coverage, and connectivity issues, as well as increased hardware complexity. There are further studies to address this problem involving a large array of sensors. For instance, tactile sensors mounted on flexible PCBs around robot arms for human-robot interactions [26], [27] demonstrate the feasibility of using multiple sensors. However, these approaches lack synchronized sensor reading and involve large setups (around 80 cm), making them impractical to use for our application.

Addressing these limitations, our work proposes the design of a novel perception system consisting of 12 VL53L8CX time of flight sensors from STMicroelectronics [28]. These sensors are distributed between two SPI buses operating at 4 MHz to give a consistent reading throughout. Due to its multi-zone sensing ability, we use this array of sensors to generate a sparse point cloud representation of the quadcopter’s surrounding area, which is then used for collision avoidance while flying inside a ballast tank. This approach overcomes previous limitations by offering a synchronized, scalable, and lightweight perception solution specially tailored for compact aerial vehicles operating in confined, featureless, and cluttered environments. The overall system architecture of the designed aerial vehicle is shown in Figure 2.

II. HARDWARE SETUP

The main objective of this paper is to develop a highly effective yet low-cost perception system for confined space operations. A quadcopter is designed to accommodate all required sensors, out of which 10 are mounted around the circumference of the quadcopter, one is placed at the top plate facing upward, and one at the bottom plate facing downward. The circumferential sensors are carefully placed to cover a 360° field of view around the quadcopter without interfering with or overlapping individual sensor fields of view. The sensors are divided into two SPI buses, and both buses are interfaced with a Teensy 4.1 microprocessor, selected for its ample RAM (1024KB) and high processing speed, driven by

Fig. 2: System architecture showing overview of basic components used.

a 600 MHz ARM Cortex-M7 suitable for simultaneous data handling from all sensors. Each sensor module is connected to a custom-made PCB Figure 4, designed to reduce the noise during the initialization and reading phase. On the processor side, the MISO, MOSI, and clock signal lines for each bus are integrated with external buffers, capacitors, and resistors to amplify the signal for consistent distance reading. Two buffers of type SN74LVC125A (SOIC 14) are used on the processor side PCB for each bus. These buffers are driven by ground (GND) and handle all the signal lines. Whereas, on the sensor-side PCB, individual buffers are implemented with individual lines, which are driven by chip select (CS). This design ensures that the Teensy identifies only one active sensor per bus during initialization. The Teensy runs a micro ROS node to collect all the data from the sensors and publish it to a Jetson Orin NX via micro USB.

Crucially, all 12 sensors are synchronized using an external synchronization pin, which triggers all the sensors simultaneously during the reading phase. This is vital for accurate real-time perception and localization, as sequential reading introduces latency, potentially causing drift and unintended vehicle motion. To verify this synchronous property of the ToF sensor setup, an experiment is performed as shown in Figure 3. A universal robotic arm is used to move the target attached to the flatbed facing upwards. The target is then moved vertically in a periodic motion such that it covers the field of view of all sensors every time. The frequency of the movement of the robotic arm is aligned with the frequency of reading, i.e. 1Hz, for proper visualization. As shown in the figure, the distance measurements from all the sensors are exactly the same at each reading loop. This confirms active synchronization, underscoring the proposed system’s suitability for real-time perception applications.

Fig. 3: Experimental setup for the synchronization feature of VL53L8CX sensor. The left image shows the robotic arm attached to the target facing all 12 sensors. The right image gives the graphical representation of synchronized distance measurement over time.

Fig. 4: Custom-made PCB to house Teensy 4.1 and VL53L8CX. 1. Front part where microcontroller is placed along with DC-DC converter. 2. Back side where transistors and buffers are attached. 3. Front view of the sensor housing. 4. Rear part for sensor housing with a connector to the SPI line.

III. METHODOLOGY

The raw readings obtained from the sensors in the multi-array are processed and transformed into suitable frames for geometric interpretation. The VL53L8CX Time-of-Flight (ToF) sensor measures distances in a fixed grid pattern, where an 8×8 configuration is used throughout this study. Each zone returns a distance measurement d_{ij} , where $i, j \in \{0, 1, \dots, 7\}$. The distance measurements, along with the corresponding zone IDs, are returned by the sensor to the microcontroller. These IDs are useful for customizing the measuring pattern on the grid based on the application.

Each distance d_{ij} corresponds to a direction in the sensor's frame, defined by the horizontal and vertical angles (ϕ_j, θ_i) of that zone. Conceptually, the sensor behaves analogously to a pinhole projection model, similar to the intrinsic geometry of perspective cameras. In this model, the rays corresponding to each pixel originate from a single optical center (sensor origin) and diverge based on fixed angular offsets. The angular offsets (ϕ_j, θ_i) map each zone to a ray in 3D space.

According to the pinhole model, the 3D coordinates of a point in the sensor frame \mathcal{F}_s can be recovered by projecting

the range reading d_{ij} along the corresponding ray:

$$x_{ij} = -d_{ij} \cdot \tan(\phi_j) \quad (1)$$

$$y_{ij} = -d_{ij} \cdot \tan(\theta_i) \quad (2)$$

$$z_{ij} = d_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Here, the z_{ij} component aligns with the optical axis (sensor's forward direction), while x_{ij} and y_{ij} correspond to lateral and vertical displacements, respectively, induced by angular offsets ϕ_j and θ_i . The use of the $\tan(\cdot)$ function reflects the small-angle approximation consistent with angular projections in the pinhole model. Negative signs are included to align with the sensor's axis conventions.

Alternatively, for small angles (typically less than $\pm 15^\circ$), a linearized planar approximation can be used to simplify calculations. In this approximation, each pixel zone is treated as occupying a fixed location in the image plane at a normalized depth, and the real-world displacement is scaled linearly with depth:

$$x_{ij} = \Delta x \cdot (j - 3.5), \quad y_{ij} = \Delta y \cdot (i - 3.5), \quad z_{ij} = d_{ij}$$

Here, $\Delta x, \Delta y$ are per-pixel spacings (in meters) at 1 meter depth, and 3.5 represents the center index of the 8×8 grid. This planar method is computationally simpler and works well for low-divergence fields of view.

1. Rigid Body Transformation to Base Frame

Each sensor is mounted at a known position and orientation relative to the drone's base frame, denoted as \mathcal{F}_b (base-link in this case). Let \mathcal{F}_s denote the local sensor frame. Then the point expressed in the sensor frame can be denoted as:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_s} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ij} \\ y_{ij} \\ z_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^3$$

To express this point in the base frame, we apply a rigid-body transformation using the known extrinsic calibration (e.g., from URDF or static TFs). The transformation is composed of a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ and a translation vector $\mathbf{t}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_b} = \mathbf{R}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_s} + \mathbf{t}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} \quad (4)$$

This transformation can also be expressed in homogeneous coordinates:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_b} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} & \mathbf{t}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b} \\ \mathbf{0}^T & 1 \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{T}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{\mathcal{F}_b}} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_s} \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

2. Filtering and Point Cloud Aggregation

To ensure accurate perception for obstacle avoidance, sensor readings are filtered to exclude invalid returns caused by internal and external noise. Readings are refined based on criteria like distance range, height bounds, and an initialization error flag. The range for valid distance is kept within

Fig. 5: Wireframe diagram of the model showing placement and axes of the sensors relative to body frame \mathcal{F}_b . The z -axis represents the measuring (optical) axis.

$0.01 < d_{ij} < 3.5$ as sensor accuracy decreases at greater distances; however, these thresholds can be adjusted based on operational requirements. Additionally, when the drone operates near surfaces such as the ground or ceiling, height-based filtering is crucial to prevent the circumferential sensors from falsely detecting these surfaces as lateral obstacles. Furthermore, improper initialization of any sensor is flagged based on the discrepancy in the reading while generating the fused point cloud. Then, the valid set from all N sensors is aggregated as:

$$\mathcal{P} = \bigcup_{k=1}^N \left\{ \mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_b}^{(k)} \mid \text{valid}(\mathbf{p}_{\mathcal{F}_s}^{(k)}) \right\} \quad (6)$$

This set \mathcal{P} forms the final fused 3D point cloud used for downstream tasks such as mapping, navigation, and collision prevention. In ROS 2, this is published as a point cloud or depth message relative to the body frame.

Fig. 6: Validation of the transform and field of view coverage for the sensors in an enclosed environment.

IV. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

This section describes the architecture of the simulation environment for the designed framework based on the application of collision prevention. This work uses software

in the loop (SITL) for PX4 and interacts through Gazebo and QGroundControl. PX4 firmware has two primary layers: the flight stack, which manages core functionalities such as state estimation, control, navigation, and guidance; and the middleware, which handles communication. As part of the middleware, we use the micro Object Request Broker (uORB), which is a publish-subscribe messaging system that enables asynchronous data exchange between PX4 modules.

Sensor data from the gazebo simulator is transmitted via Gazebo plugins over predefined user datagram protocol (UDP) ports. To replicate the VL53L8CX sensor, the plugin for 3D GPU-Lidar is trimmed along the horizontal and vertical axes based on the effective field of view of the sensor. The sample, range, and resolution are also selected based on a sensor. PX4 SITL listens on these ports, acquires the data through the simulator module, and routes it via uORB to use by internal modules. Similarly, actuator commands generated by PX4 are sent back to Gazebo, closing the control loop.

1. Comparison with 2D LIDAR Baseline in Simulated Ballast Tank

To benchmark the performance of the proposed multi-sensor VL53L8CX-based collision prevention system, a comparative study is conducted against a traditional 2D LIDAR-based setup using the Hokuyo URG-04LX. A confined ballast tank is simulated in Gazebo, modeled with structural features such as vertical longitudinal, narrow passageways, and metallic surfaces that typically interfere with range sensors.

For the first setup, we employ 12 VL53L8CX TOF sensors arranged radially on the drone, as explained above, which provides 768 zoned depth readings per cycle. Then the points for every sensor are discretised into 180 sectors of 2° each, covering a full 360° horizontal field. For each sector, the closest obstacle point is extracted and used to populate a synthetic 2D laser scan. Empty sectors are assigned a maximum range value (i.e., 4 m) to indicate free space. The resulting scan message is converted into a PX4-compatible obstacle distance message, encoding the range in each sector and the corresponding angular resolution. After that, the drone is commanded using velocity setpoints via the trajectory setpoints interface. During the simulation, a forward velocity command is sent to move towards a predefined goal while obstacles are introduced into the field of view of the ToF sensors. A manual off-board control is written to slow down and stop in the direction of detected obstacles if the drone is as close as 0.5 m. For comparison, in the next step, a forward-facing 2D LIDAR is mounted on the top of the drone, which generates a 360-degree planar scan at a fixed height. Its data is converted from the laser scan format to a point cloud, and the same procedure is applied as in the case for the TOF sensor setup. The drone is then commanded to move to a target position such that it encounters the wall with longitudinals on its way.

2. Point-Cloud Map Comparison with 3D LIDAR system

To assess the spatial fidelity of the proposed sensor setup, side-by-side flights of our prototype quadrotor Figure 1 and a

Fig. 7: PX4 SITL simulation result for the designed model in the collision prevention case. fig. 7a Virtual ballast tank world along with the model carrying both ToF sensor setup and Hokuyo URG-04LX LiDAR. fig. 7b shows the scenario with ToF sensors set up, preventing the drone from moving further towards the wall. fig. 7c 2D LiDAR could not sense the incoming longitudinal and ultimately collide with it.

commercially available Flyability Elios3 drone, equipped with a high-resolution rotating 3-D Ouster LiDAR, were performed inside the ballast tank. As part of a data collection, both drones are made to hover and yaw for a certain period of time inside the ballast tank. The obtained point clouds are processed to extract only 10 frames from each data stream. The reason behind these tests is to see the sparsity and reliability of the sensors' reading during the real flight and not the mapping. Figure 8 contrasts representative point clouds obtained from both platforms.

V. DISCUSSION

From the simulation result, it is clearly observed that the sensor setup with VL53L8CX outperforms the Hokuyo URG-04LX 2D LiDAR in terms of collision prevention in an environment like a ballast tank. Figure 7 demonstrates the active collision prevention using both the TOF sensor setup and the 2D LiDAR. Since VL53L8CX uses a planar grid of 8×8 , it is able to detect the extruded longitudinals on the wall of the ballast tank, which is the case in real-world scenarios. The algorithm for collision prevention works on binning and extracting the closest point in that sector, which makes it perceive extrusion from the wall. Even though the 2D LiDAR

works on the same algorithm, if the longitudinal do not lie on the same plane as the LiDAR, it cannot detect it and ultimately collide with it. Hence, the LiDAR system works only if the drone is flying at an altitude where the ranging plane of LiDAR matches the plane of extrusion of the obstacle. Hence, it is safe to say that the LiDAR performs adequately in open corridors; it fails to detect narrow beams and edges of long vertical structures that protrude into the drone's path, leading to delayed evasive actions or side collisions. In contrast, the proposed ToF sensor array maintained collision-free navigation in all test scenarios.

Furthermore, the fused TOF map provides sufficient features for scan-matching-based pose refinement. The reduced density primarily affects mapping fidelity rather than safety-critical avoidance, demonstrating that a lightweight, low-power multi-TOF configuration can be a viable alternative in confined metallic and cluttered environments where size, weight, and cost constraints preclude a full 3D LiDAR. It can be observed Figure 8b that if the VL53L8CX sensors are placed strategically, we can obtain a sparse fused point cloud sufficient for spatial awareness of the environment.

Fig. 8: Visual comparison of accumulated ten point-cloud maps inside the mock ballast tank. fig. 8a is the model of the actual ballast tank where the drone is flown. fig. 8b shows the sparsity of points collected from the ToF sensors setup. fig. 8c Denser pointcloud from 3-D Ouster LiDAR from Elios3 drone.

TABLE I: Comparative Attributes of Candidate Systems.

	TOF Sensor Setup		Hokuyo URG-04LX (2D LiDAR)	Ouster (3D LiDAR)
	Teensy 4.1	12 × VL53L8CX		
Operating Voltage (V)	4.9	3.2	5	12
Operating Current (A)	0.07	0.88	0.5	1.5
Power Consumed (W)	0.343	2.816	2.5	18
Flight Time (min.)		7.8	8.1	4
Weight (gm)		140	160	1100

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the design and implementation of a novel perception system based on multiple VL53L8CX Time-of-Flight sensors and validates its applicability through both simulation and real-world scenarios in confined spaces. The proposed sensor system leverages the multi-zone distance measuring capabilities, offering a promising lightweight alternative to conventional LiDAR-based perception methods. Through a series of experiments and validation tests, we demonstrate that the developed sensor configuration is effective and reliable for real-time obstacle avoidance and feedback control applications. Additionally, future research will focus on integrating sensor fusion techniques with a lightweight visual system for optimal trajectory planning during ballast tank inspection.

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